

Digital Infrastructure Transformation: Challenges and Initiatives of a Third-Class Municipality in Pursuit of Good Governance

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Abstract

In the 21st century, the world has become more digitalized, and technology has become an important instrument in promoting good governance. This study investigated the levels of efficiency of the digital initiatives and digital transformation, their relationship, and the challenges encountered in the adoption of digitalization in the Municipality of Pilar, Capiz, in pursuit of good governance. It is grounded on the assumption that Pilar, a third-class municipality have digital initiatives as it adopts the electronic Local Government Unit system and is anchored theoretically on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology. The sequential explanatory mixed-method approach was used with a verified and reliable interview guide and questionnaire created by the researcher. There were 397 respondents, all residents from 24 barangays. Eight municipal implementers were the participants of the study. Results showed that the municipality's level of effectiveness of digital infrastructure initiatives, such as the availability of digital public services, internet connectivity and network development, and Information Communication Technology facilities, was recognized as moderately effective. While the effectiveness of digital transformation on good governance also showed a moderately effective result, with responsiveness being the highest aspect. Findings also revealed a high positive relationship between digital infrastructure initiatives and the level of digital transformation of good governance. Despite the challenges, like a lack of infrastructure, limited training for staff, and a lack of funding, it has been proven that digital transformation contributes to improving the transparency, responsiveness, and accessibility of public services.

Keywords: *Digital Infrastructure Transformation, Good Governance, Digital Public Services.*

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Introduction

Digital transformation is ubiquitous in every aspect of life, from communication and interaction to service. The rapid growth of technology has created changes, offering public administration the flexibility and ease of access in providing services to individuals and organizations, as emphasized by Jakob and Krcmar (2018) and Mergel et al. (2019). In the Philippines, digital transformation changes the way public administration serves and assists the local citizens. One strategy established was the Digital Transformation Strategy 2022, which optimizes the process of delivering public services by utilizing Information and Communications Technology (ICT).

As an action towards promoting digital governance, the Department of Interior and Local Government initiated the eLGU among the three island groups covering Luzon, Visayas, and Mindanao. This initiative led to more than 344 Local Government Units (LGUs) pledging to adopt the system. As of this day, around 41 cities and 901 municipalities utilize the eLGU system, emphasizing that many other LGUs still use manual processes. The local governments are continuously facing uncertainties and drastic changes

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in responding to address people's needs. In all efforts to implement digital solutions, they are bound to navigate various barriers, including limited resources, resistance to change, and the need for adequate training and support for personnel (Bokolo, 2021). In the Municipality of Pilar, Capiz, Philippines, a third-class municipality, various services are provided in compliance with the Anti-Red Tape Act. Aside from the general public services, the municipality also offers a Women's Program, Senior Citizen Program, Solo Parent Program, Differently-Abled Persons Program, Indigent Program for PhilHealth Beneficiaries, and Public Employment Service Office. These services aimed to provide accessible and responsive services to their constituents, aligning with the principles of good governance.

Furthermore, despite the significant contribution of digital infrastructure, a gap remains, particularly in rural areas. Several studies have focused on national levels and urban cities, leading to limited knowledge on the challenges, effectiveness, and initiatives of digital transformation in smaller Local Government Units (LGUs). Additionally, even though there are existing strategies and initiatives that have been established, there is no clarity in terms of the integration, implementation, and utilization of relevant and modern digital infrastructures in the actual operation at the local level. Building on the gaps, there is a scarcity of research in relation to examining the relationship between digital transformation and good governance in municipal settings. Highlighting this gap is essential to address the issue across local areas.

Thus, the study's main goal was to examine the digital infrastructure transformation in the third-class municipality of Pilar, Capiz, as a pursuit of good governance. By examining the current public administration digital transformation landscape, this research understands the challenges and initiatives towards good governance in the digital age. Moreover, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) was employed to investigate how public administration employees accept and use digital systems. It highlights the importance of digital infrastructure initiatives and perceptions towards digitalization for successful and effective digital services. The UTAUT was utilized to analyze the transformation of digital infrastructure in municipal local government units, identifying the aspects affecting the successful digital governance implementation.

The study investigated the challenges and initiatives of the digital infrastructure transformation of a third-class municipality in pursuit of good governance. Even with the potential advantages of digital transformation, there remain unresolved issues.

Methodology

A sequential explanatory mixed-method approach, which incorporates aspects of both qualitative and quantitative methods, was employed. The chosen design was suitable and appropriate, as it allowed the researcher to gather numerical data measuring the level of the effectiveness of digital infrastructure, digital infrastructure initiatives, and correlations of the variables. It allowed an in-depth exploration of the primary challenges encountered by the Municipality of Pilar in implementing digital infrastructure transformation, as identified by municipal implementers. The researcher can validate results, effectively address several facets of research topics, and present a more comprehensive picture of communication dynamics by incorporating the method (Creswell & Plano-Clark, 2011).

The quantitative phase employed the quantitative cross-sectional survey design to identify the level of effectiveness of digital transformation initiatives and its correlation to good governance. Additionally, quantitative research was deemed suitable for this study due to its ability to reflect reality more accurately through the analysis of a large volume of data, which enhanced the representativeness of the results. Moreover, it supported the generalization of findings and enabled the researcher to make predictions about future outcomes. Meanwhile, in the qualitative phase, a descriptive approach was used to provide accurate and detailed descriptions of the participants' answers during the interview. According to Creswell and Creswell (2020), the descriptive research design is suitable for studies that aim to describe the phenomenon or characteristics. It is used for understanding a certain problem.

The Municipality of Pilar, Capiz, was the location of this investigation. It is a third-class municipality selected for its unique challenges and ongoing initiatives in digital infrastructure transformation. As a third-class municipality, Pilar, Capiz, is burdened with the lack of resources, especially in digital infrastructure in the local governance. Thus, this research aimed to examine the specific challenges the local government faced in implementing digital infrastructure changes and evaluate the initiatives undertaken to overcome these challenges.

The participants in this study were clients and implementers of government services to evaluate digital transformation experiences and efficiency in service delivery. The clients or customers were those who had availed themselves of the services of the government, while the implementers were the frontline service providers, encompassing the local government employees who were responsible for delivering services. The key participants were the 397 residents of Pilar, Capiz, from all 24 barangays. In the quantitative phase, 397 respondents were surveyed according to demographic variables: respondents aged 18–60 years old, with no particular gender, with no specific educational attainment, and with required experience in accessing municipal services and online public services, internet connectivity and network infrastructure, and ICT infrastructure. In the qualitative phase, the participants included the eight municipal implementers from the municipal government of Pilar.

A survey questionnaire was used for data collection, translated into the local language for clarity, and it was developed so that participants could respond to the fundamental questions on the topics being studied. In the qualitative phase, the researcher prepared an interview guide, which was validated by a panel of experts.

After securing approval, the researcher finalized the survey questionnaire and conducted a pilot test to assess its validity and reliability. Revisions were made based on the feedback received from the pilot test. The finalized questionnaires were then distributed to the selected participants, such as barangay officials and other respondents identified through stratified random sampling. Throughout the data collection period, the researcher monitored response rates and sent reminders to non-respondents to encourage participation. In the qualitative phase, in-person interviews were used to obtain qualitative data. In order to guarantee the validity of the selection, the researcher personally invited the participants, provided them with the objectives and goals, and informed them about the research and made sure that they were comfortable in the process. For the conduct of the in-depth interview, the researcher used the prepared facilitating set of questions. After the survey and interview period ended, all completed questionnaires and interview recordings were collected, organized, and cleaned by removing incomplete or inconsistent responses. To ensure confidentiality, the data were anonymized before being analyzed using statistical software to address the research objectives and generate the findings.

Quantitative data analysis included descriptive statistics and inferential statistics to summarize demographic characteristics and trends. This study used statistical methods, such as T-tests or ANOVA. The findings were then integrated into a report, highlighting key findings and their implications for local government agencies and good governance. On the other hand, qualitative data underwent thematic analysis. This study integrated the Six-Step Data Analysis Process of Clarke and Braun in 2006.

Results and Discussion

Level of Effectiveness of Digital Infrastructure Initiatives in the Municipality of Pilar

Results showed that when respondents were taken as a whole group, the digital infrastructure initiatives in terms of availability of digital public services were moderately effective in Pilar as indicated by the total mean score of 3.15. The availability of digital public services, with a mean of 3.15, interpreted as “moderately effective,” showed that there were online and digital services in the municipality that residents could access and use, but these were not fully improved and enhanced despite their availability to the public. There are still limitations, such as in user-friendliness, in the digital services provided by the local government. This aligned with the performance expectancy of the Unified Theory of

Acceptance and Use of Technology of Venkatesh et al. (2003), stressing that individuals use technology that is available and they feel that it can provide benefits to them and make their lives easier. The moderate effectiveness of the digital infrastructure initiatives emphasizes the need for improvements.

Level of Effectiveness of Digital Infrastructure Transformation on Good Governance

Result revealed a grand mean of 3.29, which indicates that the majority of residents moderately favor the effectiveness of digital infrastructure initiatives. This implies that despite the limitations of technical equipment, internet connectivity, and accessibility, residents are still able to take advantage of services and experience positive changes in governance through digital platforms. Looking at the three dimensions, responsiveness obtained the highest mean of 3.37, which shows that residents perceive that the local government responds quickly and continues to resolve problems and complaints with digital services. Service transparency with a mean of 3.35, followed in the second position, which implies that there is a moderate level of trust that the public has about the stability and openness of the service on digital platforms. Finally, accessibility with a mean of 3.15 obtained the lowest, which shows that although there is an improvement in access to digital services, more is needed to ensure that more residents can use the service without difficulty, especially in rural areas and among people who lack digital skills.

Results confirmed the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology by Marikyan and Papagiannidis (2021), which performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions affect the acceptance and use of technology. The moderately favorable perception of the residents shows that they enjoy the benefits of digital services, but the ease of use, availability of support, and usability of the system still need enhancements to further develop good governance.

Relationship Between the Levels of Effectiveness of Digital Infrastructure Initiatives and Digital Infrastructure Transformation on Good Governance

Results revealed a strong relationship between the levels of effectiveness of digital infrastructure initiatives and digital infrastructure transformation on good governance ($r = 0.726$, $p = 0.000$). The Pearson r value of 0.726 indicated a high to very high relationship, and since the p -value was less than 0.05, thus statistically significant. The result implies that as digital infrastructure initiatives in the Municipality of Pilar are developed and strengthened in relation to and the level of effectiveness of digital infrastructure transformation impact on good governance also increases.

The Technology Acceptance Model developed by Fred Davis (1989) supported the findings, which states that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are the main factors in the acceptance of technology. If the digital services of the municipality are seen as useful and easy to use, the level of trust and approval of the people in the digital transformation initiatives will increase. Therefore, the strong relationship observed in the study confirms that an effective digital infrastructure is an important foundation for achieving good governance in the Municipality of Pilar.

Further, the results provide the need to improve the effectiveness levels of both the digital initiatives and digital transformation, all for good governance of the Municipality of Pilar, a third-class municipality. Meaning, efforts and actions will draw from the gaps along the various statements towards the “very effective” level.

Primary Challenges Encountered by the Municipality of Pilar in Implementing Digital Infrastructure Transformation

Based on the thematic analysis, the main challenges faced by the Municipality of Pilar in the implementation of digital infrastructure transformation could be grouped into four major themes: infrastructure and technical limitations, human resource challenges, financial and organizational constraints, and service accessibility and user engagement.

In terms of infrastructure and technical limitations, Participants indicated brownouts and weak internet connections as problems, problem of expanding digital services in the municipality of Pilar, viewing these as a hindrance to effective and efficient transformation and digitalization. This implies that the lack of

stable electricity and internet connection is a major obstacle to the effective implementation of digitalization.

In terms of human resource challenges, Participants mentioned the lack of training and seminars for employees, fear, and the lack of experience, showing that there are psychological and competency barriers within the organization.

Furthermore, in terms of financial and organizational constraints, it is clear that the budget was one of the biggest problems they encountered. Participants indicated the need for a clear organizational structure and hiring qualified personnel to support maintenance and system upgrades.

In terms of service accessibility and user engagement, even though most of the participants mentioned that their service is transparent and accessible, there are still issues such as the digital divide and lack of coordination among agencies.

The results imply that even if there is a digital system, not all residents have the same capacity to use it. In general, the results showed that the most urgent solution is to provide comprehensive training to employees, strengthen the internet and power infrastructure, provide an adequate budget, and improve coordination between departments to make the digital infrastructure transformation effective and inclusive in the Municipality of Pilar.

Insights on Good Governance

Based on the findings, it can be seen that digital infrastructure initiatives play a significant and positive role in promoting good governance in the Municipality of Pilar. The strong correlation ($r = 0.726$) indicates that as digital infrastructure, such as internet connectivity, Information Communication Technology (ICT) facilities, and digital public services, is strengthened, residents' positive perceptions of the transparency, responsiveness, and accessibility of local government also increase. This shows that technology is not just a support mechanism but a strategic instrument to strengthen accountability and efficiency in public service delivery.

Second, the results show that transparency and responsiveness depend on the quality and smoothness of digital systems' implementation. Despite the moderately effective level of digital transformation, issues such as lack of funding, limited technical expertise, and resistance to adopting new technologies remain. This means that good governance requires a comprehensive approach, including strengthening the capacity of employees through training, providing clear strategic direction, and ensuring that there is sufficient budget for digital transformation. This is to say that digitalization transforms administrative processes, breaking down the dysfunctions in the local government, increasing efficiency in public service delivery, paperless and more cost-effective

Third, the study provides insight that inclusivity and investment in digital literacy are important aspects of good governance for data-driven decision making and enhanced citizen engagement and trust. Despite the availability of digital services, not all residents have equal access to the internet, devices, and digital skills. The presence of the digital divide means that digital transformation must be inclusive and citizen-centered. There is a need to strengthen internet infrastructure, improve coordination between departments, and create programs that assist residents with limited technological knowledge.

Conclusion

Digital infrastructure transformation in the Municipality of Pilar is essential in advancing good governance. Despite the challenges, it demonstrates ongoing efforts and notable progress toward improving digital public service delivery. This highlights that successful digital transformation requires not only technological investment but also strengthened human resources, financial capacity, organizational readiness, and citizen engagement. The effectiveness of digital infrastructure transformation, particularly in terms of service transparency, responsiveness, and accessibility, plays a crucial role in promoting accountability, efficiency, and inclusivity in public service delivery. Despite

existing limitations such as inadequate technical structure, limited personnel training, insufficient funding, and unequal access to technology, the municipality has achieved moderate effectiveness in the implementation of digital infrastructure initiatives, including the provision of digital public services, improved internet connectivity, and the development of Information and Communication Technology. The strong relationship between the level of effectiveness of digital infrastructure initiatives and digital infrastructure transformation in the Municipality of Pilar implies that as digital infrastructure initiatives are developed and strengthened, the level of effectiveness of digital infrastructure transformation on good governance also increases. In the local context, the study emphasizes the importance of improvements, changes, and development for effective and inclusive public services. It provides a practical and evidence-based perspective that can be used as a guide for other local governments to strengthen their digital governance methods and action plans. The findings serve as a basis for policy enhancement and developing programs. The importance of this study cannot be undervalued, offering support for optimizing transparency and accountability and encouraging continuous reform of local legislation.

Conflict of interests

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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